

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DIALLO****FIRST NAME: GAELLE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The method of academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 9; 1-14)
2. The structure of academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 10-14)
3. The rules of style (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
4. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34)

EXPECTATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As I embarked on this doctorate program through Euclid University, I had to review all the documents provided in this first course. The content of the course pack offers a strong base on the expectations for the program. It relates to the standards expected by all students to follow. Those standards include writing skills, text formatting, the rules of style, understanding plagiarism, and referencing methods. Having students write about the materials they study in this first course should help them build a solid foundation for the entire program.

This first assignment aims to get acquainted with the academic writing skills required at EUCLID University. In this paper, I will discuss the method of academic writing, the structure of academic writing, the rule of style, the chosen language, plagiarism, and referencing techniques.

2) THE METHOD OF ACADEMIC WRITING

As this first course introduced me to international academic essay writing, it set the tone for the methodology. Writing an academic essay includes understanding the topic, researching relevant information, brainstorming, organizing ideas, and creating a plan for the paper (EUCLID 2021, 1-14).

Once the research topic is recognized and the question identified, the student must target their reading materials. The suggested readings are a starting point. It can be broadened with other relevant library materials (EUCLID 2021, 9). Furthermore, the researcher is strongly encouraged to develop critical thinking skills and provide opinions and impressions from the documents. Building a good argument on a topic is a way to discover other views, compare ideas and develop analytical thinking.

As the ideas are forming, the next step will consist of elaborating a plan to answer the research question and structure the essay accordingly (EUCLID 2021, 9). It is recommended that the researcher aligns the findings with the research question and uses the most relevant information gathered. The writing will need to flow and ideas to connect. A well-written essay would have been started early with a constant prompt of the research topic and a final proofread.

This first step was laborious as it relates strictly to writing rules. Although it provided me with the regulations and expectations from an academic perspective, it was dry material to read. However, reading the materials made the prospect of this academic degree a reality.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC WRITING

The goal of having a framework for academic essays is to standardize and provide consistency in the presentation of the work (EUCLID 2021, 10-14). The format includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. In the introduction, the writer launches the topic to help readers identify what they will read about. Depending on the research method, the introduction could also refer to a research question. A summary of what will be discussed in the main body needs to be mapped.

A series of paragraphs will constitute the main body of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10). This section will include the details of the main ideas, the arguments, and the evidence to support the discussion. In this section, the writer will be able to demonstrate their knowledge of the topic throughout a structured discussion using strong evidence, providing analysis and interpretation of data. The writer will prove their ability to follow the rules of academic writing by using quotations and referencing accordingly.

In the conclusion section, the author restates the answer to the question elaborated in the introduction, summarizes the main points discussed, and includes a final statement indicating a possible need for further research (EUCLID 2021, 10).

4) THE RULES OF STYLE

A style guide is a method to document the researcher's technique for collecting information (EUCLID 2021, 41). Academic writing requires a dedicated style guide that will facilitate the reading and understanding of the paper.

At Euclid University, the style guide refers to the Chicago style. With its specifics, the Chicago style highlights and is not limited to the formatting of the text, the use of abbreviations, quotations, footnotes, and tables. The goal is to standardize the writing to ensure consistency and facilitate proofreading (EUCLID 2021, 41-42).

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

English has evolved and gone through different socio-political influences (EUCLID 2021, 25). Whether one uses the American or British English version, one must abide by the specific language rules.

For this academic, I chose to use the American version. Although British English has always influenced my previous school experience, I have worked in an environment under strong American English dominance. This will mean paying attention to the vocabulary and spelling of words, as well as setting the proofreading in the appropriate American English version.

6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is a form of appropriation of work or ideas from another source. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). Academic writing requires integrity from the writer. The writer must maintain that honesty by always giving credit to the used citations, quotes, and even when paraphrasing.

Academic writing aspires to convey knowledge most intellectually with impartiality to the broader academic community. Therefore, the researcher must be transparent about their sources of evidence when they make a claim. Integrity in academic research reflects the researcher's responsibility and ethics. Using Grammarly software is a safety net to mitigate the risk of plagiarism.

7) CONCLUSION

Writing an academic essay requires a standardized approach to the methodology. The writer needs to grasp all the steps of a well-structured paper, from gathering ideas and planning the structure of the essay to proofreading. Different tools are available to the

student, such as proofreading and plagiarism checkup software, to provide a comprehensive and authentic document.

REFERENCES

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